

Analysis of Leading Commodities of the Agricultural Sector and Strategies for Development of Regional Economic Potential in Bojonegoro Regency 2015-2019

Ita Handayani, Slamet Kyswanto
Development Economics - Bojonegoro University

Abstract:- The agricultural sector is one sector that has opportunities in economic development activities. The existing sub-sectors in the regions need to be developed as potential sectors. Bojonegoro Regency as one of the regions in East Java Province has a considerable opportunity in developing its regional potential to increase economic development in Bojonegoro Regency. This study aims to examine the potential of Bojonegoro Regency, the competitiveness of each subsector, and determine the leading sector in Bojonegoro Regency. This study uses secondary and primary data. Secondary data is sourced from BPS (Central Bureau of Statistics), while primary data is sourced from employees of the Department of Agriculture. How to obtain data with the method of documentation and questionnaires. The data is processed using Location Question analysis techniques to determine commodities that have a comparative advantage, while commodities that have competitive advantages are analyzed using the Shift Share Analysis (SSA) method, and SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) to determine strategies for developing regional economic potential . . Location Quotients analysis results show that the agricultural sector includes four sub-sectors, namely food crops, horticulture, plantations and livestock. The food crop sub-sector which is the leading commodity in Bojonegoro Regency is rice paddy. The vegetable horticulture sub-sector which is the main commodity is shallots and tomatoes. The fruit horticulture sub-sector which is the main commodity is Mango and Papaya. The plantation sub-sector which is the leading commodity is Tobacco (Virginia, Java, RAM). And the Livestock Sub-sector which is the leading commodity, namely cows and free-range chickens. Based on the calculation of Shift-Share Analysis analysis, it is known that commodities that have competitive competitiveness and experienced growth in 2015-2019 include: The food crops sub-sector consists of lowland rice (Sekar, Bubulan, Temayang, Kedungadem, Baureno, Balen, Bojonegoro, Gayam, Malo, Purwosari, Kasiman), Corn (Kedungadem, Baureno), Peanut (Ngasem, Malo), and Soybean (Cotton). The vegetable horticulture sub-sector consists of Shallots (Sekar, Bubulan, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Kepoh Baru, Sumberrejo, Balen), Chile (Margomulyo, Ngraho, Tambakrejo, Ngambon, Trucuk, Padangan), Tomatoes (Ngraho, Temayang). The fruit horticulture sub-sector consists of Mango (Ngambon, Bubulan, Temayang,

Sugihwaras, Kepohbaru, Baureno, Cotton, Ngasem, Purwosari, Kedewan), Salak (Kapas, Dander), Orange (Sugihwaras, Dander), Banana (Papaya, Ngambon), Tambakrejo, Ngambon, Gondang, Temayang, Baureno, Balen, Bojonegoro, Trucuk, Dander, Ngasem, Kalitidu, Kedewan), Papaya (Margomulyo, Ngambon, Sekar, Bubulan, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Baureno, Kanor, Sukosewu, Bojonegoro, Trucuk , Dander, Gayam, Kalitidu, Malo, Purwosari, Padangan, Kedewan). The plantation sub-sector consists of Virginia tobacco (Kedungadem, Kepohbaru, Baureno, Kanor Sukosewu), Javanese tobacco (Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem), Sugarcane (Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Sumberrejo). The livestock sector consists of cattle (28 sub-districts), buffalo (Ngraho, Temayang, Ngasem, Kedewan), horses (Sumberrejo, Bojonegoro), goats (Margomulyo, Ngraho, Ngambon, Sekar, Bubulan, Gondang, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem , Kepohbaru, Kanor, Sumberrejo, Balen, Sukosewu, Cotton, Bojonegoro, Trucuk, Ngasem, Gayam, Kalitidu, Malo, Purwosari, Kasiman, Kedewan), Lamb (Ngraho, Ngambon, Sekar, Bubulan, Gondang, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Kepohbaru, Kanor , Sumberrejo, Balen, Sukosewu, Cotton, Bojonegoro, Trucuk, Ngasem, Kalitidu, Malo, Purwosari, Kasiman, Kedewan), Kampung Chicken (Margomulyo, Ngraho, Tambakrejo, Ngambon, Sekar, Bubulan, Gondang, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Kepohbaru, Kanor, Sumberrejo, Balen, Sukosewu, Cotton, Bojonegoro, Trucuk, Ngasem, Gayam, Kalitidu, Malo, Purwosari, Kasiman, Kedewan), Laying hens (Kedungadem, Kepohbaru, Kanor, Balen, Kapas, and Ngasem), Broilers (Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Baureno, Kanor, Sumberrejo, Balen, Sukosewu, Ngasem, K alitidu, Ma lo), Ducks (Margomulyo, Ngambon, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Baureno, Kanor, Sumberrejo, Balen, Sukosewu, Ngasem, Kalitidu, Malo), Mentok (Ngambon, Sekar, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Baureno, Sumberrejo, Dander , Gayam, Kasiman), Pigeons (Margomulyo, Ngambon, Sekar, Bubulan, Gondang, Temayang, Sugihwaras, Kedungadem, Kepohbaru, Kanor, Balen, Cotton, Ngasem, Padangan, Kasiman), Quail (Kalitidu). Strategies that must be applied in developing regional economic potential in Bojonegoro Regency in the agricultural sector are Making appropriate technology by applying environmentally friendly technology, creating

economic networks at the rural level to take advantage of potential agricultural resources, developing agricultural facilities and infrastructure, developing human resources for farmers through extension programs. agriculture, creating agricultural businesses that .

Keywords:- Agriculture, Leading Sub-sector, Commodity, Development Strategy.

I. INTRODUCTION

National development is an effort to improve the quality of human life and Indonesian society which is carried out continuously based on national capabilities by utilizing advances in science and technology and taking into account the challenges of global development. Indonesia's National Development has the goal of realizing a just and prosperous society.

Regional economic development is a process in which the government regions and community groups manage resources which exist and form a pattern of partnership between local government and the sector private to create something field work new and stimulate development activity economy in region the (Arsyad, 2002). form economy area which built reflect enhancement community role and service Public with purpose main is improve the welfare of society.

The agricultural sector is an *engine of growth*, both in terms of providing raw materials, employment opportunities, food and as purchasing power for products produced by other sectors. naturally economic development must be supported by the development of the agricultural sector which strong good from side offer nor side request. From side supply, the agricultural sector must be able to create a production surplus that profitable for producers and can be helped back in activities production that is reinvested in high production activities and create activity industry which focus on ability the agricultural sector as a source of investment and a provider of raw materials for industry which concerned. From side request is Agriculture which strong should create a request potential for product the agricultural sector itself product activity other which no generated by sector other (Sumodiningratand Mudrajat: 19).

Development goals Agriculture is to increase production and quality results which Empower competitive tall in skeleton reach endurance food and opportunity market, Upgrade opportunity work and try, increase the income and welfare of farmers and their families through agribusiness other especially in the countryside, Upgrade quality Public farming and human resources to support successful development Agriculture and push development economy rural through the development of competitive agribusiness systems and businesses and sustainable.

The leading sector (base) is the sector that is the backbone of the regional economy because it has a fairly high *competitive advantage*. While the non-base sector are other sectors that are less potential but function as a support for the base sector or *service industries* (Sjafrizal, 2008:89). One indicator of determining the leading sector in a region can be seen from the contribution of the largest added value of a sector in the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP), so that the aggregate output (goods and services) or Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) is known every year.

Population growth push the need for adequate food supply more big so that production Agriculture should improved. Enhancement production Agriculture achieved with enhancement productivity caused because limited land and time (Salim, 1986:32). Program enhancement ingredient food directed for fulfil food needs. Food security is a very strategic and important. Food is needs tree at a time Becomes essence human life, therefore the right to food is a very important part of human rights basic man. Endurance food is part from endurance national which moment this rated Very fragile. Development endurance food in Indonesia in Law number 7 of 1996 concerning food as a efforts to achieve food availability for all households, in sufficient quantity, proper quality and nutrition, safe for consumption, evenly distributed and affordable by each individual.

According to Tjokroamidjojo (1987:12) "in making development changes must be based on systematic planning, because with this planning an alternative choice process will be selected from various options to achieve certain goals". If it is related to this research, after identifying the leading sector/base, it is necessary to have a strategic plan and economic development strategies in developing the most superior/superior sector in Bojonegoro Regency.

Sector economy which influence development area in district Bojonegoro is sector Agriculture which covers sub sector plant ingredient food, vegetables sub-sector, fruits sub-sector, sub-sector sector plantation, sub sector farm and fishery sub-sector. Determination superior commodity area is wrong a factor of economic development. In fact almost in all the area has superior commodities. Development superior commodity in all areas not entirely successful because it is still low financing. Based on the description above, this study intends to analyze about commodity superior sector Agriculture in district Bojonegoro so that could utilized in process development economy area. The objectives of this research are:

- To study agricultural commodities which are the mainstay of the economy in Bojonegoro Regency.
- To analyze strategy which should applied in development regional economic potential in Bojonegoro Regency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A. *Theoretical basis*

➤ *Definition of Economic Development*

Development economy could interpreted as activities carried out by a region to develop economic activities and level life people.

➤ *Regional Economic Development Concept*

The regional development model is defined as a framework of thinking that objective and rational based on concepts, theories and paradigms in the form of strategic To use solve problem in Public.

➤ *Growth Regional Economy*

Growth economy region is increase income Public by whole which occur in region the, that is increase in all *value added* that occurred in the region.

➤ *Agricultural Development*

Role sector Agriculture in development economy very important because part big population in countries poor hang life in this sector

➤ *Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP)*

GRDP is defined as the amount of added value generated by all business units in an area or is the total value of the final goods and services produced by all economic units in a region (BPS, 2005).

- according to Approach Production (*Production approach*)
- according to Approach Income (*Income approach*)
- according to Expenditure Approach (*Expenditure Approach*)
- according to Method Allocation (*Allocation method*)
- Theory Base Economy (*Economic Base Theory*)
- ✓ Method direct
- ✓ Method no direct
- ✓ Method mixture
- ✓ Method *Location Quoient (LQ)*

➤ *Previous research*

➤ *conceptual framework*

Framework this start from analysis commodity superior sector agriculture . Where the agricultural sector commodities in Bojonegoro include the food crops sub-sector, plantation sub-sector, horticulture sub-sector and subsector farm.

This study also analyzes agricultural commodities that have a competitive advantage in an area by method compare commodity superior area and show connection between an area with a higher population, for example compare Among Bojonegoro District with Bojonegoro Regency

This study uses a type of quantitative-qualitative research. This qualitative research was conducted by providing an overview of the regional potential of the agricultural sector. Quantitative research uses 2 (two) analytical methods. The data used are in the form of secondary data and primary data. Secondary data sourced from the Central Bureau of Statistics of Bojonegoro Regency. While the primary data sourced from employees of the Department of Food Security and Agriculture of Bojonegoro Regency.

Extraction of primary data information is done by means of structured interviews using a questionnaire. The research location is in Bojonegoro Regency, which is one of the regencies in East Java Province.

The data that has been collected is researched and analyzed using the following analytical tools:

A. *Location Quotient (LQ)*

Location Quotient (LQ) method is a method that is often used as an indication of the base sector which is then used as an indication of the leading sector. *Location Quotient* method is a comparison of the magnitude of the role of a sector in an area against the role of a sector nationally or in a sub-district sector to the role of a sector at the regional or district level. To find out the leading agricultural commodities in the Bojonegoro Regency, a comparison is made using the following equation (Hendayana, 2003)

$$LQ = \frac{p_i / p_t}{P_i / P_t}$$

Description:

LQ : Index *Location Quoient*

p_i : p production of commodity i at level districts

p_t : number of commodity subsector i in district level

P_i : total production of commodity i on district level

P_T : total commodity subsector i in district level

The measurement criteria for the resulting LQ value are as follows:

1) $LQ > 1$	: State sub-region concerned have potency export in activity certain.
2) $LQ < 1$	: Indicates the relevant sub-region hastrend import from sub-region other.
3) $LQ = 1$	: Shows the area in question is sufficient in activity certain (balanced).

Various basic measures in the use of LQ must be adjusted to the interests of research and available data sources. If the research is intended to look for sectors/sub-sectors whose economic activities are contributed by the sector, then the value of the GRDP is used as the basis for the measurement, while to look at the leading/base commodities,

the number of production results of the selected commodity can be used as a basis.

B. Commodity Competitive Advantage Analysis (Shift Share)

SSA analysis is used to determine food crops sub-sector commodities that have a competitive advantage, with positive SSA criteria. Mathematically, the SSA method is formulated as follows (Rustiadi *et al.* 2011):

$$SSA = \left(\frac{X_{...}(t1)}{X_{...}(t0)} - 1 \right) + \left(\frac{Xi(t1)}{Xi(t0)} - \frac{X_{...}(t1)}{X_{...}(t0)} \right) + \left(\frac{X_{ij}(t1)}{X_{ij}(t0)} - \frac{Xi(t1)}{Xi(t0)} \right)$$

(a) (b) (c)

Where:

a = component *regional share*

b = component *proportional shift*

c = component *differential shift*

X.. = value total activity in total region

Xi = value total activity certain in total area

X_{ij} = value activity certain in units certain area

t₁ = point of last year

t₀ = year point beginning

C. SWOT Analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats)

The methodology of this research consists of several stages, namely:

- Preliminary data collection regarding regional economic potential development strategies
- Followed by a literature study about decision support methods, starting from the determination, alternatives, criteria, weight of criteria.
- Determination of variables in SWOT analysis (identification of internal and external factors)

- Create a list of Opportunities, Threats, Strengths, and Weaknes (adjusted to conditions in the field)
- Determine the weight of each factor starting from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree), adjusted to the results of data collection.
- Determine the rating of each factor from 1.0 (very important) – 0.0 (not important) in the column adjusted to the results of the interview
- Multiply the weight and rating
- Create a weighted score per factor to generate a total score
- Determination of Rating, Weight, Score
- SWOT Matrix Strategy combination calculation
- Calculate Normality from step 5. calculation
- Based on the results of the 6th stage calculation, select internal and external factors to be the criteria and weights in decision support.
- Putting the criteria, sub-criteria and alternatives into a pairwise comparison matrix, a pairwise comparison matrix resulting from comparisons between predetermined criteria and alternatives.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Location Quotient (LQ) Analysis Results

Location Quotient analysis is an analytical tool to find out the leading sub-sectors and which are not the leading sub-sectors. This can be seen if (LQ > 1) means that the sub-sector is a leading sub-sector. Then if (LQ < 1) means that the sub-sector is not a leading sub-sector.

Based on the results of the LQ calculation of agricultural sector commodities in Bojonegoro Regency, the following results were obtained:

➤ *Food Crops Subsector*

Table 1 LQ Value of Food Crops Subsector Production

No	districts	Rice Paddy	Corn	Cassava	Peanuts	Mung beans	Soya bean	Sweet potato
1	Margomulyo	0.35	3.82	1.31	0.01	0.06	0.72	0.00
2	Ngraho	0.96	1.22	0.27	0.04	0.01	1.56	0.06
3	Tambakrejo	0.49	2.87	4.63	0.46	0.03	1.14	0.00
4	Ngambon	0.40	2.26	15.66	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	now	0.23	3.89	6.42	0.29	0.09	0.02	0.04
6	moon	0.26	4.14	1.01	9.63	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	Gondang	0.56	3.08	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00
8	Theme	0.84	1.81	0.11	0.15	0.00	0.65	2.28
9	Sugihwaras	1.19	0.32	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.43	0.00
10	Kedungadem	1.11	0.72	0.12	0.00	1.48	0.03	0.28
11	New Kepoh	1.23	0.17	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.18	1.55
12	Baureno	1.22	0.23	0.16	0.03	1.26	0.07	0.00
13	Kanor	1.26	0.06	0.12	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00
14	Sumberejo	1.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.73	0.00
15	Balen	1.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	3.02	0.00

16	Sukosewu	1.25	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.00	1.33	0.00
17	Cotton	1.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.41	2.07	0.00
18	Bojonegoro	1.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
19	truck	1.03	0.88	0.05	0.00	0.11	0.00	47.74
20	Dander	1.12	0.42	0.00	10.80	2.48	1.13	0.00
21	suck	1.01	0.70	4.15	1.19	7.30	0.21	0.55
22	Gayam	1.23	0.19	0.20	0.53	0.29	0.00	0.00
23	Kalitidu	1.25	0.12	0.02	0.34	0.39	0.00	0.00
24	Malo	0.97	1.11	1.90	0.73	3.09	0.08	0.00
25	Purwosari	0.88	1.65	0.12	0.13	2.66	0.42	0.00
26	field	1.27	0.00	0.06	2.31	0.00	0.02	0.00
27	Kasim	0.93	1.48	0.01	1.40	2.00	0.00	0.00
28	Council	0.78	2.15	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

➤ *Horticulture Sub Sector (Vegetables and Fruits)*

Table 4.2 Horticulture (Vegetables) Subsector LQ Value Table

No	districts	Onion Red	Chilli	Peanut Long	Tomato	Eggplant	Mustard greens etc
1	Margomulyo	0.21	0.94	33.15	11.85	3.13	0.23
2	Ngraho	0.17	0.50	7.27	16.46	5.11	1.77
3	Tambakrejo	0.10	0.50	3.90	0.90	5.35	4.89
4	Ngambon	0.16	3.67	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00
5	now	1.66	0.00	0.43	0.19	0.10	0.00
6	moon	1.64	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	Gondang	1.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
8	Theme	1.24	0.48	9.08	10.15	0.37	0.16
9	Sugihwaras	0.79	2.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Kedungadem	1.65	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	New Kepoh	1.63	0.11	0.95	0.25	0.01	0.00
12	Baureno	0.00	0.29	0.45	0.00	5.03	10.93
13	Kanor	0.04	1.48	29.18	58.32	1.32	0.63
14	Sumberejo	1.60	0.13	0.00	4.78	0.00	0.00
15	Balen	1.33	0.13	0.00	0.00	1.37	0.54
16	Sukosewu	1.67	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
17	Cotton	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.84
18	Bojonegoro	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
19	truck	0.02	2.62	3.53	48.19	0.62	1.27
20	Dander	1.62	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
21	suck	0.00	4.04	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00
22	Gayam	0.00	0.39	31.02	5.49	1.24	17.96
23	Kalitidu	0.04	0.93	46.53	5.43	3.44	0.50
24	Malo	1.26	0.12	13.40	9.67	0.56	0.93
25	Purwosari	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	8.08	1.16
26	field	0.00	0.02	0.57	0.69	6.43	7.42
27	Kasim	0.00	0.09	46.21	2.70	0.45	20.78
28	Council	0.00	3.22	0.96	19.03	0.98	0.00

Table 3 Value of LQ in the Horticulture Fruits

No	districts	Mango	snakefruit	Orange	Banana	Pawpaw	Star fruit
1	Margomulyo	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.65	12.57	34.76
2	Ngraho	2.10	0.00	0.00	0.74	1.25	0.04
3	Tambakrejo	0.07	0.00	0.00	1.26	0.11	0.00
4	Ngambon	0.06	0.00	0.04	1.27	0.07	0.00
5	now	0.06	0.00	0.00	1.25	1.57	0.00
6	moon	3.79	0.00	0.00	0.26	5.69	0.21
7	Gondang	0.31	0.00	0.00	1.20	0.00	0.04
8	Theme	4.87	0.00	2.92	0.05	0.45	0.30
9	Sugihwaras	0.29	0.00	88.63	1.08	6.11	0.51
10	Kedungadem	3.31	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.32	0.17
11	New Kepoh	5.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.73	0.22
12	Baureno	0.98	0.00	0.00	1.02	0.81	0.29
13	Kanor	3.19	0.00	0.00	0.26	17.63	0.45
14	Sumberejo	3.46	0.00	0.00	0.41	0.00	0.22
15	Balen	1.46	0.23	0.00	0.91	0.19	0.23
16	Sukosewu	0.27	0.00	0.00	1.12	7.54	0.00
17	Cotton	0.25	13.42	0.00	1.06	2.26	0.06
18	Bojonegoro	3.64	0.00	0.00	0.22	11.96	0.40
19	truck	0.70	0.00	5.79	1.01	3.62	5.18
20	Dander	0.38	51.13	65.84	0.65	0.46	0.10
21	suck	3.27	0.00	0.00	0.46	0.00	0.26
22	Gayam	1.54	0.00	0.00	0.66	19.23	0.34
23	Kalitidu	0.64	0.00	0.00	0.67	3.80	47.91
24	Malo	3.71	0.00	0.00	0.16	15.52	0.54
25	Purwosari	2.83	0.00	0.00	0.57	0.18	0.02
26	field	1.30	0.00	0.00	0.91	2.52	2.04
27	Kasim	1.98	0.00	0.00	0.75	2.56	0.27
28	Council	0.10	0.00	0.00	1.24	1.13	0.12

➤ Plantation Sub-Sector

Table 4 LQ Value of Plantation Subsector

No	districts	TOBACCO			Sugar cane	Coconut
		Virginia	Java	RAM		
1	Margomulyo	0.00	0.00	0.02	1.06	1.07
2	Ngraho	0.00	0.69	3.49	1.20	0.91
3	Tambakrejo	0.47	1.40	2.15	0.88	1.10
4	Ngambon	0.49	1.27	1.85	0.07	1.70
5	now	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00	1.83
6	moon	0.00	1.74	0.00	0.00	1.78
7	Gondang	0.00	0.17	0.00	0.00	1.84
8	Theme	0.00	4.81	0.00	0.81	1.06
9	Sugihwaras	2.45	2.68	1.11	1.74	0.29
10	Kedungadem	1.63	0.89	0.66	2.10	0.16
11	New Kepoh	14.48	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.48
12	Baureno	3.81	0.09	0.00	0.86	0.96
13	Kanor	8.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.33
14	Sumberejo	5.13	0.05	0.00	0.76	0.96

No	districts	TOBACCO			Sugarcane	Coconut
		Virginia	Java	RAM		
15	Balen	0.11	0.10	0.00	0.00	1.84
16	Sukosewu	2.95	3.06	0.03	0.09	1.47
17	Cotton	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.85
18	Bojonegoro	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.43	0.06
19	truck	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.90	1.18
20	Dander	0.08	0.49	0.00	1.15	0.98
21	suck	1.47	4.86	2.40	0.52	1.16
22	Gayam	0.16	0.72	20.42	2.18	0.05
23	Kalitidu	0.00	0.12	0.13	0.44	1.52
24	Malo	0.26	0.34	0.25	1.33	0.83
25	Purwosari	0.01	1.70	3.02	1.86	0.39
26	field	0.00	0.13	0.58	1.80	0.52
27	Kasim	0.00	0.15	2.36	0.93	1.14
28	Council	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	1.76

➤ Livestock Sub-Sector

Table 5 LQ Value of Livestock Subsector

No	districts	Cow	Buffalo	Horse	Goat	Sheep	Kampong chicken	Laying Chicken	Broiler	Duck	stuck	Pigeon	Quail
1	Margomulyo	0.49	0.16	0.00	0.65	0.34	1.26	0.07	0.98	0.20	0.26	0.12	0.00
2	Ngraho	3.75	3.45	0.00	3.28	3.69	1.55	0.12	0.06	0.66	0.57	0.60	0.00
3	Tambakrejo	3.19	0.74	0.00	2.70	1.00	1.06	0.10	0.04	1.33	0.00	11.26	1.41
4	Ngambon	6.22	0.42	0.00	3.99	3.47	1.50	0.00	0.00	1.57	1.35	0.71	0.00
5	now	3.73	0.09	0.00	3.74	2.57	1.27	0.00	0.00	4.46	5.17	1.92	0.00
6	moon	1.59	5.91	0.00	3.65	3.19	1.22	3.32	0.36	0.56	0.00	0.61	0.65
7	Gondang	1.63	4.35	0.00	2.76	2.08	1.04	2.54	0.57	2.59	0.90	0.85	2.36
8	Theme	1.62	12.12	0.16	3.19	0.81	1.47	0.00	0.17	1.53	3.03	0.37	3.06
9	Sugihwaras	0.77	1.62	0.00	0.83	0.67	1.66	0.00	0.41	0.98	1.79	0.28	0.00
10	Kedungadem	0.92	0.15	0.02	0.76	0.73	0.45	2.43	1.57	1.49	2.04	0.65	1.48
11	New Kepoh	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.36	0.71	1.12	1.43	0.65	0.00	1.82	0.49
12	Baureno	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.26	0.46	0.24	1.87	0.44	0.41	0.01	0.04
13	Kanor	0.39	0.00	0.35	0.75	0.76	0.57	1.92	1.50	1.94	0.96	0.31	0.03
14	Sumberejo	0.30	0.00	0.75	0.64	0.79	0.91	0.56	1.25	0.25	0.40	0.89	0.08
15	Balen	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.79	1.39	2.03	0.70	0.54	0.83	0.36	1.26
16	Sukosewu	0.95	0.00	0.00	1.03	0.53	1.56	0.00	0.47	0.44	1.37	0.00	0.00
17	Cotton	0.86	0.00	0.71	0.51	0.98	1.09	1.84	0.86	2.58	0.00	1.18	0.54
18	Bojonegoro	0.85	0.00	3.69	0.77	1.21	1.63	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.74	1.04	22.34
19	truck	1.15	0.00	0.00	0.67	0.87	0.40	1.35	1.58	2.90	0.95	0.81	0.00
20	Dander	1.44	0.42	1.07	2.27	1.92	0.84	0.34	0.84	0.45	1.68	1.10	9.97
21	suck	3.42	3.07	1.59	2.46	2.00	1.33	5.18	0.18	2.01	3.23	1.40	0.22
22	Gayam	2.43	0.24	0.00	1.32	5.03	1.18	1.31	0.35	1.30	3.28	0.53	0.00
23	Kalitidu	2.38	0.13	1.02	1.05	1.31	0.95	0.00	1.10	1.14	0.00	0.47	1.64
24	Malo	2.01	1.48	5.43	1.71	1.48	1.09	0.18	0.73	1.36	1.20	1.71	1.74
25	Purwosari	2.04	3.05	27.59	0.66	2.44	1.77	0.00	0.21	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.00
26	field	2.08	0.45	9.36	1.33	0.45	1.73	0.00	0.04	0.22	0.41	4.11	0.88
27	Kasim	1.00	1.62	0.72	0.77	0.83	0.98	3.19	0.93	0.65	2.99	1.26	0.91
28	Council	1.67	12.78	0.00	1.42	0.32	1.82	0.00	0.00	0.96	0.69	2.18	0.55

B. Shift Share Analysis of Food Crops Sub-Sector

Agricultural sector that own superiority competitive determined based on Mark SSA positive.

Case this refers to to component SSA which covers *regional share* (rate growth total region), *proportional shift* (growth total activity certain by relatively compared with total

activity region), and *differential shift* (level competition activity certain compared growth total activity in region). It means, if cumulative regional share, *proportional shift*, and *differential shift* is positive so commodity the experience growth so that have a competitive advantage. The results of the SSA analysis are presented in the table below:

➤ *Shift Share Analysis of Food Crops Sub-Sector*

Table 6 SSA Analysis Crop Sub-Sector Food in Bojonegoro Regency 2015 – 2019

No	districts	Ssa Food Crops Sub Sector						
		Rice Paddy	Corn	Cassava	Peanuts	Mung beans	Soya bean	Sweet potato
1	Margomulyo	-0.25	-0.79	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	Ngraho	-0.09	-0.98	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3	Tambakrejo	-0.92	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.98	0.00
4	Ngambon	-0.99	-0.99	-0.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	now	0.28	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	moon	0.35	-0.99	0.00	-0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	Gondang	-0.01	-0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
8	Theme	0.16	-0.89	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.81	0.00
9	Sugihwaras	-0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Kedungadem	0.26	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	New Kepoh	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.96	0.00
12	Baureno	0.09	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
13	Kanor	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	Sumberejo	-0.66	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.74	0.00
15	Balen	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
16	Sukosewu	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
17	Cotton	-0.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.56	0.00
18	Bojonegoro	0.32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
19	truck	-1.00	-0.98	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.94
20	Dander	-0.99	0.00	0.00	-0.78	0.00	-0.81	0.00
21	suck	-0.84	-0.98	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00
22	Gayam	1.30	-0.94	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
23	Kalitidu	-0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
24	Malo	0.05	-0.64	0.00	13.36	0.00	0.00	0.00
25	Purwosari	0.31	-0.91	0.00	-0.28	0.00	-0.98	0.00
26	field	-0.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
27	Kasim	0.67	0.30	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
28	Council	-0.74	-0.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

➤ *Results of Shift Share Analysis of Horticulture (Vegetables) Sub Sector*

Table 7 SSA Analysis Horticulture (Vegetables) sub-sector in Kabupaten Bojonegoro 2015 – 2019

No	districts	Horticulture Sub Sector (Vegetables)					
		Shallot	Chilli	Long beans	Tomato	Eggplant	Mustard greens etc
1	Margomulyo	0.00	9.67	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00
2	Ngraho	0.00	0.67	-1.00	2.05	-1.00	0.00
3	Tambakrejo	0.00	17.60	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00
4	Ngambon	0.00	29.31	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00
5	now	0.60	0.00	-1.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
6	moon	9.45	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	Gondang	-0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

No	districts	Horticulture Sub Sector (Vegetables)					
		Shallot	Chilli	Long beans	Tomato	Eggplant	Mustard greens etc
8	Theme	-0.31	-0.80	-1.00)	1.22	-1.00	0.00
9	Sugihwaras	2.38	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Kedungadem	2.49	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	New Kepoh	11.32	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00
12	Baureno	0.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
13	Kanor	0.00	-0.87	-1.00	-0.90	-1.00	0.00
14	Sumberejo	0.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
15	Balen	7.53	-1.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
16	Sukosewu	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
17	Cotton	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
18	Bojonegoro	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
19	truck	0.00	66.83	0.00	-0.10	-1.00	0.00
20	Dander	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
21	suck	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
22	Gayam	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
23	Kalitidu	0.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00
24	Malo	0.00	0.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00
25	Purwosari	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
26	field	0.00	0.64	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	0.00
27	Kasim	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
28	Council	0.00	-0.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 8 SSA Analysis Horticulture (Fruits) sub-sector in Bojonegoro Regency 2015 – 2019

No	districts	Fruits Sub Sector					
		Mango	snakefruit	Orange	Banana	Pawpaw	Star fruit
1	Margomulyo	-1.00	0.00	0.00	1.27	0.12	-1.00
2	Ngraho	-0.00	0.00	0.00	1.49	0.00	-1.00
3	Tambakrejo	-0.46	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00
4	Ngambon	1.58	0.00	-1.00	390.92	-1.00	-1.00
5	now	-1.00	0.00	0.00	-0.19	-1.00	0.00
6	moon	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.66	-1.00
7	Gondang	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.38	0.00	0.00
8	Theme	3.49	0.00	-0.53	0.18	0.31	-1.00
9	Sugihwaras	6.97	0.00	0.49	-0.39	1.90	-1.00
10	Kedungadem	-0.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00
11	New Kepoh	187.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12	Baureno	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.61	-1.00
13	Kanor	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.96	-0.99	0.00
14	Sumberejo	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
15	Balen	-0.72	0.00	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00
16	Sukosewu	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.98	-1.00	0.00
17	Cotton	1.72	0.76	0.00	-0.54	0.00	-1.00
18	Bojonegoro	0.00	0.00	0.00	35.2	65.75	0.00
19	truck	0.00	0.00	-1	11.68	-0.13	-1.00
20	Dander	-1.00	30.65	178.38	16.02	-1.00	-1.00
21	suck	1.41	0.00	0.00	3.17	0.00	-1.00
22	Gayam	-1.00	0.00	0.00	-0.15	-0.63	-1.00
23	Kalitidu	-0.98	0.00	0.00	0.01	-0.93	-1.00
24	Malo	-1.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00	-0.72	-1.00
25	Purwosari	17.76	0.00	0.00	-0.04	-1.00	-1.00
26	field	-0.66	0.00	0.00	-0.44	3.60	-1.00
27	Kasim	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
28	Council	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.20	1.12	-1.00

➤ Results of Shift Share Analysis of the Plantation Sub-Sector

Table 9 SSA Analysis Plantation sub-sector in Bojonegoro Regency 2015 – 2019

No	districts	Plantation Sub-Sector				
		Virginia Tobacco	Java Tobacco	Tobacco RAM	Sugarcane	Coconut
1	Margomulyo	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.07	-1.00
2	Ngraho	0.00	-1.00	-0.93	-0.59	-1.00
3	Tambakrejo	-1.00	-1.00	-0.58	-0.60	-1.00
4	Ngambon	-1.00	-0.55	-0.74	0.00	-1.00
5	now	0.00	-0.11	0.00	0.00	-1.00
6	moon	0.00	-0.71	0.00	0.00	-1.00
7	Gondang	0.00	-0.51	0.00	0.00	-1.00
8	Theme	0.00	1.82	0.00	-0.35	-1.00
9	Sugihwaras	-0.44	2.13	-0.41	0.47	-1.00
10	Kedungadem	2.27	1.65	0.00	0.34	-1.00
11	New Kepoh	0.80	0.00	0.00	-0.67	-1.00
12	Baureno	2.12	-1.00	0.00	-0.26	-1.00
13	Kanor	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00
14	Sumberejo	-0.34	0.00	0.00	2.25	-1.00
15	Balen	-0.79	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00
16	Sukosewu	11.35	5.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00
17	Cotton	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00
18	Bojonegoro	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
19	truck	0.00	0.74	0.00	-0.88	-1.00
20	Dander	0.00	-0.39	0.00	-0.50	-1.00
21	suck	-1.00	4.05	0.00	-0.90	-1.00
22	Gayam	-1.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
23	Kalitidu	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00
24	Malo	-0.18	-0.13	0.00	-0.42	-1.00
25	Purwosari	0.00	-0.51	-0.21	-0.63	-1.00
26	field	0.00	-1.00	-0.59	-0.10	-1.00
27	Kasim	0.00	-1.00	-0.51	-0.66	-1.00
28	Council	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.78	-1.00

➤ Results of Shift Share Analysis of Livestock Sub-sector

Table 10 SSA Analysis Livestock sub-sector in the District Bojonegoro Year 2015 – 2019.

No	districts	LIVESTOCK SUB SECTOR											
		Cow	Buffalo	Horse	Goat	Sheep	Kampong chicken	Chicken Pete	Spicy Chicken	Duck	tock	Pigeon	Quail
1	Margomulyo	0.28	-1.00	0.00	0.21	-0.20	12.21	0.00	-0.88	0.80	0.00	2.65	0.00
2	Ngraho	0.17	0.14	0.00	0.21	1.33	0.07	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00
3	Tambakrejo	0.24	-1.00	0.00	0.47	-0.81	0.25	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	-1.00	-1.00
4	Ngambon	0.23	-1.00	0.00	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.03	1.24	0.00

No	districts	LIVESTOCK SUB SECTOR											
		Cow	Buffalo	Horse	Goat	Sheep	Kampong chicken	Chicken Pete	Spicy Chicken	Duck	tock	Pigeon	Quail
5	now	0.24	-1.00	0.00	0.19	0.25	0.10	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.26	6.83	0.00
6	moon	0.21	-1.00	0.00	0.19	0.02	0.17	-0.33	0.00	-0.01	0.00	1.17	0.00
7	Gondang	0.33	-0.16	0.00	0.26	0.21	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.43	-	0.88	1.22
8	Theme	0.23	0.15	-1.00	0.19	0.28	0.10	0.00	0.25	0.88	0.84	0.95	-1.00
9	Sugihwaras	0.24	-0.47	0.00	0.24	0.07	0.07	0.00	1.07	0.75	1.08	0.94	0.00
10	Kedungadem	0.25	-1.00	0.00	0.28	0.27	0.18	1.86	0.33	1.14	-	1.28	0.00
11	New Kepoh	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.00	0.04	0.75	-0.12	-1.00	0.00	0.85	0.00
12	Baureno	0.24	0.00	0.00	-	0.09	-0.16	-0.88	0.00	1.52	2.46	3.11	-1.00
13	Kanor	0.23	0.00	-1.00	0.26	0.33	0.16	1.21	0.52	1.08	-	1.75	0.00
14	Sumberejo	0.15	0.00	0.50	1.88	1.45	0.24	-0.71	0.54	-1.00	7.29	-1.00	-1.00
15	Balen	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.28	0.15	0.34	0.36	1.61	-	2.97	0.00
16	Sukosewu	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.15	0.14	0.00	1.48	-1.00	-	0.00	0.00
17	Cotton	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.27	0.33	1.50	-0.15	0.84	0.00	1.10	-1.00
18	Bojonegoro	0.22	0.00	3.50	0.33	0.17	-0.03	0.00	0.00	-1.00	-	-1.00	-1.00
19	truck	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.52	1.05	0.00	0.00	-0.43	0.00	0.00	-1.00
20	Dander	0.33	-1.00	-1.00	-	0.02	-0.02	-0.84	-1.00	0.00	-0.20	1.92	-0.89
21	suck	0.24	0.02	-1.00	0.27	0.57	0.17	3.42	1.50	0.41	-	0.34	2.86
22	Gayam	0.22	-1.00	0.00	0.20	-0.04	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.77	2.01	-1.00	0.00
23	Kalitidu	0.22	0.00	-1.00	0.30	0.20	0.09	0.00	0.48	5.19	0.00	0.00	2.99
24	Malo	0.23	-0.56	0.00	0.15	0.21	0.06	0.00	1.50	0.95	-	1.00	-1.00
25	Purwosari	0.25	-0.11	-0.03	0.18	0.17	0.06	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
26	field	0.23	0.00	-0.09	-	0.40	0.11	0.11	0.00	0.00	-1.00	0.00	0.16
27	Kasim	0.23	-1.00	-1.00	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.32	1.93	0.26	0.00
28	Council	0.24	0.01	0.00	0.29	0.28	0.12	0.00	0.00	1.26	-	1.00	-0.45

C. Regional Economic Potential Development Strategy in Bojonegoro Regency

After seen from strength, weakness, opportunity and threat from factor internal and external, evidently sector agriculture has a strong internal potential, then the factors strategy internal in the form of existence technology in field Agriculture, availability group farmer in every village, potency source pownatural which adequate and breadth land Agriculture considered own superiority comparative.

These two elements of good internal and external potential should not be released just like that, but will become the main issue development. Although thus, in the process the study no can forgotten to various obstacles and threats change condition environment which there is around, in an effort to maintain a comparative advantage the, of them existence pest and disease plant, unstable price production Agriculture, failure harvest and decrease large land Agriculture.

V. CONCLUSION

A. Quantitative Research Results

From the results of data analysis that has been carried out, the following conclusions can be obtained:

- Based on the results of *Location . analysis Quotients* in the 2015-2019 period, it was concluded that in Bojonegoro Regency there were commodities that were identified as superior because of their wide distribution, Food Crops Sub-sector, namely Lowland Rice (16 Districts), Horticulture Sub-Sector consisting of vegetables and fruits. Vegetables are onions and tomatoes while fruits are mango and papaya. The plantation sub-sector is tobacco (Virginia, Java and RAM). Livestock sub-sector, namely cows and native chickens.
- Based on calculation analysis *Shift-Share Analysis* is known that commodities that have competitive competitiveness and experience growth based on the amount of production and population in 2015-2019 include the food crops sub-sector consisting of competitive lowland rice in 11 sub-districts, competitive corn in 3 sub-districts, competitive peanuts in 2 Districts, Competitive Soybeans in 1 District. The vegetable horticulture sub-sector consists of competitive shallots in 7 sub-districts, competitive chili in 6 sub-districts, and competitive tomatoes in 2 sub-districts. The fruits sub-sector consists of competitive mangoes in 10 sub-districts, competitive Salak in 2 sub-districts, competitive oranges in 2 sub-districts, competitive bananas in 14 sub-districts, and competitive papaya in 8 sub-districts. The Plantation sub-sector consists of competitive Virginia Tobacco in 5 districts, competitive Java Tobacco in 6 districts, and competitive Sugarcane in 3 districts. The Livestock sub-sector consists of competitive cattle in 28 sub-districts, competitive buffalo in 4 districts, competitive horses in 2 districts, competitive goats in 24 districts, competitive sheep in 23 districts, competitive kampung chickens in 25 districts, and laying hens.

B. Qualitative Research Results

Strategy which should applied in development potency economy area in Bojonegoro Regency, namely the manufacture of technology appropriate To use with apply technology friendly environment, create network economy leveled rural To use exploiting the potential of agricultural resources, developing facilities and infrastructure Agriculture, development HR farmer through program agricultural extension, creating agricultural businesses that are oriented towards agribusiness, development technology control pest integrated, development of assistance programs for rural economic enterprises (LUEP) and enhancement utilization technology as well as quality results Agriculture.

SUGGESTION

The government of Bojonegoro Regency is expected to be able to increase the superiority of agricultural sector commodities by taking into account the conditions of production factors, conditions, market demand, supporting industries and related industries, company strategy, structure and competition, opportunities and the role of the government itself.

- The government's role is needed to increase the productivity of superior commodities
- Provision of fertilizers, machinery and medicines
- Provision of production facilities
- Providing agricultural commodity processing activities into processed products, both in the form and in the form of the final product.
- Provision of supporting services, both transportation and banking.

To maintain the sustainability of leading commodities so that they can be competitive to a wider market share, the following activities are needed:

- Agricultural Production and Quality Improvement
- Entrepreneurial spirit development for farmers
- Development of agribusiness partnership network
- Creating a conducive investment climate in agribusiness

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